

1 **A histone deacetylase switch featuring Hdac6 activation in dominant negative p53 mutation.**

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7 We measured total transcription in cells from tumors arising from p53-null mice and mice containing a
8 dominant negative p53 mutation (R175H) to understand the complete range of p53-associated cancer cell
9 dependencies. We report here discovery of a histone deacetylase switch associated with p53 status.
10 Cancer cells absent of p53 (p53 'null') activated *HDAC5* while cancer cells expressing a full length
11 dominant negative point mutant p53 (p53 R175H) activated *HDAC6*. Changes in epigenetic activity at the
12 chromatin accompany p53 genetic status.
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